

Crime Prevention in Modern Uzbekistan: State, Problems, Main Directions of Development

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Abstract: Crime prevention is an important aspect of maintaining law and order and stability in any State, including the Republic of Uzbekistan. In the context of political, economic and social reforms in the country, the problems of crime, especially among young people, corruption, drug trafficking and extremism, remain relevant. The purpose of this study is to analyze the state of the crime prevention system in Uzbekistan, identify problem areas and develop recommendations for improving existing methods and approaches. The research uses a comprehensive interdisciplinary approach, including methods of law, sociology, psychology and criminology, with an emphasis on the analysis of the legislative framework, the effectiveness of law enforcement agencies, as well as social and educational initiatives. It is expected that the results of the study will help to increase the effectiveness of crime prevention, improve the interaction of government agencies, public organizations and citizens, as well as contribute to strengthening the legal culture in the country.

Keywords: crime prevention, law and order, crime, youth, corruption, legal culture, sociological methods, criminology, legislation, social reforms, security, legal awareness, digitalization of prevention, crime forecasting.

Introduction

Crime prevention is one of the central components of the law and order and security system in any state [1,5]. For the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is actively undergoing a process of political, economic and social transformation, successful crime prevention directly affects the stability and development of society, strengthening the rule of law and improving the quality of life of citizens [3,4]. In recent years, the country has seen a significant improvement in the socio-economic situation, which contributes to an increase in the standard of living of the population. However, the problems of crime, including among young people, corruption, drug trafficking, extremism and other threats, continue to be relevant, requiring a careful and comprehensive approach from government agencies and the entire society.

The relevance of the topic of crime prevention in Uzbekistan is determined by a number of factors, among which the following can be distinguished:

1. "Social changes". In the context of reforms, modernization and globalization, the risks of new forms of crime are increasing. Population mobility, urbanization, the spread of the Internet and digital technologies create additional challenges for law enforcement agencies, requiring the adaptation of existing prevention methods [2].
2. "Problems of youth crime". Young people are both victims and active participants in crime. In the context of economic instability, social isolation and the lack of sufficient social mobility, the

likelihood of young people being involved in criminal activity increases, which makes the prevention of crime among young people especially relevant [7,8].

3. “The need to improve the institutional framework”. The development of a crime prevention system requires the introduction of new approaches and technologies, increased efficiency of law enforcement agencies, judicial and educational institutions, as well as the active involvement of citizens in the processes of legal awareness and legal culture [5,6,8].

4. “The growth in the number of economic and corruption crimes”. In the context of globalization and the development of market relations, the most important task is to combat economic offenses, including corruption, fraud and tax crimes. Effective prevention at all levels of government and business is becoming a necessity.

5. “Problems of legal culture and legal awareness”. The most important aspect of offense prevention is the formation of legal awareness of citizens, increasing their legal literacy and readiness to comply with laws, which requires a systematic approach in educational and upbringing work [1,4,6,7].

Thus, the problem of crime prevention in Uzbekistan is important and requires a comprehensive approach. This includes improving the social, economic and legal situation in the country, as well as improving the methods of work of law enforcement agencies and the education system. It is important that crime prevention becomes a task not only for law enforcement agencies, but also for all sectors of society, including state institutions, public organizations, the media and individual citizens.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the state of crime prevention in the modern Republic of Uzbekistan, identify the main problems that impede effective crime prevention, and develop recommendations for improving the methods and areas of preventive work in the country.

The research methodology is based on the use of a set of scientific methods aimed at a comprehensive analysis of the problem of crime prevention in Uzbekistan. To achieve the goals and solve the tasks, an interdisciplinary approach will be used, including methods of law, sociology, psychology, criminology and public administration. In particular, the following methods will be used during the study:

1. “Analysis of documents and regulations”. Assessment of the current legislation regulating crime prevention in Uzbekistan, including the Criminal Code, the Code of Administrative Offenses, as well as laws on the police, human rights and other regulations. Analysis of public policy programs, such as the Concept of Development of Law Enforcement Agencies, anti-corruption strategies and social rehabilitation programs.

2. “Comparative Analysis”. Comparison of international experience in the field of crime prevention with the practice of Uzbekistan. Study of successful examples of countries with similar socio-economic conditions to identify best practices and adapt them to the realities of Uzbekistan.

3. “Sociological Methods”. Surveys and interviews with representatives of law enforcement agencies, the judicial system, and civil society, including educational institutions, to identify the perception of existing problems and assess current approaches to crime prevention. Use of focus groups to analyze the perception of legal norms and measures taken to prevent crime.

4. “Case Method”. Study of specific cases of crime prevention in various regions of Uzbekistan to analyze successful and unsuccessful examples of the work of law enforcement agencies and social services.

5. “Criminological analysis”. Application of criminological analysis methods to identify patterns and factors contributing to crime, as well as development of prevention models based on statistical data and study of the causes of crime.

6. "Historical and legal method". Study of the history of the development of the crime prevention system in Uzbekistan, changes in legislative and law enforcement practice, as well as the evolution of approaches to combating crime within the framework of the social and legal policy of the state.
7. "Expert assessment method". Consultations with experts in the field of law, social work and criminology for a deeper understanding of existing problems and priority areas for improving the crime prevention system.
8. "Content analysis". Analysis of media materials and Internet publications to identify public opinion on law and order and the crime situation in the country.
9. "Statistical analysis". Using statistics to assess crime rates, identify trends and factors influencing crime growth.

Expected results of the study.

The results of this study are aimed at a deep comprehensive analysis and systematization of the problem of crime prevention in Uzbekistan in order to develop theoretical and practical recommendations for optimizing existing mechanisms and approaches in the field of crime prevention. The work will help identify weak links and develop solutions that will strengthen the rule of law, improve public safety and ensure effective interaction of various institutions in the process of crime prevention.

Justification of the state of the crime prevention system - to achieve the objectives of the study in this area, a comprehensive analysis of the legal and organizational structure of crime prevention in Uzbekistan is expected. The analysis will focus on the current legislation, as well as the practical application of regulatory legal acts governing this area. In particular, the effectiveness of such laws as the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility and other key legislative acts will be studied. According to Article 16 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, criminal liability for a crime occurs in the presence of guilt, but in addition, in recent years the country has adopted a number of changes aimed at improving crime prevention among young people, such as crime prevention programs aimed at preventing recidivism among minors. However, there are a number of problems in legislative practice, such as insufficient attention to the rehabilitation of offenders and not always effective use of alternative punishments (for example, correctional labor instead of imprisonment). Thus, it is important to identify the shortcomings of the current crime prevention system, such as the lack of effective prevention programs for vulnerable groups, limited opportunities for educational and public initiatives at the local level. The study will offer possible solutions to these problems, including reforming the mechanisms of interaction between public and private organizations.

2. Evaluation of the effectiveness of existing forms of prevention As part of the evaluation of existing forms of crime prevention, a comprehensive assessment of the work of law enforcement agencies, judicial and educational institutions will be conducted in the context of their participation in crime prevention. It is expected that the study will identify both successful practices and problem areas requiring improvement. Analysis of the activities of law enforcement agencies, such as the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prosecutor's Office", as well as social work with citizens, will be necessary to understand the effectiveness of existing mechanisms. In recent years, Uzbekistan has introduced a number of programs and initiatives aimed at improving interaction between law enforcement agencies and the population, such as the Safe City concept and anti-corruption programs. However, there is a problem of insufficient integration of these initiatives at the local level, as well as limited resources and personnel problems, which reduces the effectiveness of prevention. In this context, an important result of the study will be the identification of successful practices (for example, the experience of working with youth within the framework of crime prevention programs) and the analysis of bottlenecks, such as lack of

coordination between various state and public institutions. This will make it possible to develop recommendations for improving interaction and increasing the effectiveness of preventive measures.

3. Formulating recommendations for improving the prevention system. Based on the analysis, an important result of the study will be the development of proposals for improving the legal framework in the field of crime prevention. In particular, amendments to the criminal and administrative legislation will be proposed aimed at increasing liability for offenses, as well as developing institutions for social rehabilitation of criminals. In recent years, social rehabilitation systems have been actively developing in Uzbekistan, such as “Rehabilitation Centers” for drug addicts and former prisoners, but so far such initiatives do not cover all risk groups, for example, young people in socially disadvantaged conditions. The use of innovative methods, such as “digitalization of prevention” (creation of online platforms for teaching the rights and responsibilities of citizens, use of data analytics to predict crime), will be an important step towards a more effective approach. In addition, the proposed changes to the legislation will be aimed at expanding the rights and opportunities of public organizations in the field of crime prevention, as well as creating mechanisms for more effective control over the work of law enforcement agencies.

4. Improving the legal culture and legal awareness of citizens - to improve the legal culture and legal awareness of citizens, within the framework of this study, a model of an educational program will be developed aimed at increasing legal literacy among young people and other categories of citizens. It is planned to create educational courses on human rights, legality and civic responsibility both in schools and universities, as well as conduct mass information and educational campaigns. Since 2017, the national program "Legal Culture" has been actively implemented in Uzbekistan, which is aimed at increasing legal literacy among the population, but the problem remains relevant, especially among young people who are often unaware of the consequences of offenses. The program developed during the study will include both traditional and innovative forms of training, including online courses and interactive platforms. An important result will be the creation of methods for regular information campaigns aimed at reducing the level of crime by raising public awareness of legal norms and responsibility.

5. Improving work with youth at risk - the study will propose the creation of specific youth programs aimed at preventing crime among adolescents and young people. In particular, social and educational projects aimed at supporting young people in difficult life circumstances will be proposed. The Youth Against Crime program in Uzbekistan, aimed at supporting young people in conditions of social instability, is a successful example. However, the programs remain localized and do not cover all regions. The study will propose expanding such initiatives taking into account the specifics of local conditions, as well as creating more personalized social programs aimed at employment and training of young people.

6. Crime Trend Forecasting and Modeling - Using statistical and sociological methods, the study will develop crime forecasting models to predict potential risks and areas with a high probability of crime. This will enable preventive intervention and more targeted allocation of resources to combat crime. The use of big data and analytical methods to identify crime-prone areas is already being actively used in a number of countries. In Uzbekistan, the introduction of similar technologies will allow for crime surges to be predicted based on the analysis of factors such as migration flows, unemployment, poverty and social exclusion. The development of a crime forecasting model will become an important tool for law enforcement agencies and will allow for the development of more accurate crime-fighting strategies at all levels.

Conclusion:

The expected results of the study will have a significant impact on the development of the crime prevention system in Uzbekistan. The application of the developed recommendations will improve the legal framework, increase the efficiency of state and public institutions, improve

legal literacy and social adaptation of young people. Ultimately, this will lead to a decrease in crime and improvement of overall security in the country.

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